

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS

Synthesis report on performance of eLTER sites for the Whole System Approach

Deliverable D8.6

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Definition
BGC	Biogeochemistry
CS	Case Study
EBV	Essential biodiversity variable
EI	Ecosystem integrity
eLTER	Integrated European Long Term Ecosystem, critical zone and social-ecological Research
eLTER Site	Focal points for long-term ecosystem observation and research
eLTSER Platform	eLTSER Platforms represent clusters of eLTER Sites, supporting ecosystem, socio-ecological systems and critical zone research activities and providing data
GBIOS	Global biodiversity observing system
GHG	Greenhouse gases
GPP	Gross primary production
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
ICP	International Cooperative Programmes
RC	Research Challenges
RI	Research Infrastructure
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SO	Standard Observation
SOBIO	Biosphere Standard Observations
SOSOC	Sociosphere Standard Observations
TA/RA	Transnational and Remote Access
WAILS	Whole System Approach for in-situ research on Life Supporting Systems in the Anthropocene
WUE	Water use efficiency
WP	Work package

Summary

The main goal of the eLTER PLUS project is to test the emerging eLTER Research Infrastructure while challenging, assessing and strengthening its operations. More specifically, one of the objectives of the eLTER PLUS project is to test the Whole System Approach (WAILS) at the local and continental scales, focusing on exploring how long-term data of eLTER sites and platforms can provide the necessary holistic understanding of the ecosystem response to environmental and societal change. Here, we evaluated the application of WAILS using data from eLTER Sites and Platforms in different case studies (Tasks 8.1 to 8.4).

In this deliverable, we first summarise the analysis conducted and the results obtained from tasks 8.1-8.4, using a set of variables from different spheres. We found that atmosphere (e.g. temperature and precipitation) and hydrosphere (e.g. dry hydrological year and drought) predictors played a strong role as explanatory variables in the case studies conducted. We also summarise and discuss the lessons learned after working with eLTER data, the current fitness of eLTER RI and the difficulties encountered. Based on our experience with the different case studies, we have identified several key suggestions to improve the application of WAILS. For instance, it is crucial to define a set of mandatory key standard observations (SOs) to ensure consistency and comprehensiveness across different studies. Continuous data collection must be maintained to guarantee an uninterrupted flow of high-quality datasets, ensuring they remain accessible and usable for the research community. Additionally, ensuring spatial-temporal overlap between a broad range of abiotic, biotic, and socio-economic variables is necessary for the thorough implementation of WAILS. Finally, developing standardised workflows for data management, processing, sharing, and integration of legacy data will streamline the application of WAILS using data from eLTER Sites and Platforms. With the tasks carried out in this WP, we believe that being part of the eLTER RI enables unparalleled research excellence, collaboration at the European level, and attracts significant funding opportunities for eLTER Sites and Platforms.

1 Introduction

1.1 Project context and the Whole System Approach (WP8)

The eLTER PLUS project aims to enhance the development of the eLTER community, moving it towards the formal establishment of a Research Infrastructure (RI). One of the main goals of this project is to open and expand the research capacities and impact of eLTER by engaging current and new users and developing the operations of interdisciplinary research, exemplified in the eLTER Site and eLTER Platform design and the RI's Standard Observation framework. eLTER PLUS executes a performance test of the emerging RI and assesses and strengthens its operations in real time.

In the eLTER PLUS project, the Whole System Approach (WAILS) plays a leading role in fostering scientific, practical, and conceptual innovations for addressing environmental resilience and sustainable social-ecological systems. The Whole System Approach is a comprehensive, interdisciplinary approach that encompasses the Earth system including the geosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, atmosphere and social-ecological sphere. The eLTER RI implements the Whole System Approach addressing scientific and societal challenges with the goal of understanding the systemic interlinkages and feedbacks between the natural and social domains of the Earth system across spatial and temporal scales (Haberl et al. 2006, Collins et al. 2011, Singh et al. 2013, Mirtl 2018, Mirtl et al. 2021). **Figure 1** exemplifies how eLTER RI implements WAILS across sites and platforms.

Figure 1. Translating the eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI) Whole System Approach into RI design: At each eLTER in-situ facility all major components, from geosphere up to atmosphere, are covered by eLTER Standard Observations and will service the various scientific disciplines needed in cross-disciplinary research. The table in the middle represents the different categories of eLTER facilities (Sites, Platforms) and the coloured boxes indicate the relevance of given system layers in the respective categories site design. Stars indicate the level of comprehensiveness in the observation scheme. Thus, Category 1 Sites cover all ecosystem compartments and all variable groups of the eLTER Standard Observations with the basic method, and specialise on at least 2 compartments, where the prime method is accomplished. Note that the 2 selected in the figure are examples, and they can be any combination among spheres. Similarly, Category 1 eLTER Platforms will collect all SOSOCs with the prime method. Modified from project proposal (Figure 1.3.b).

One of the main goals of the eLTER PLUS project is to test the Whole System Approach at the local and continental scales, focusing on exploring how long-term data of eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms can provide the necessary holistic understanding of the ecosystem response to environmental (e.g. land use, climate change and extreme events) and societal change. More specifically, WP8 addresses the local (Site and Platform) scale while WP9 operates at larger (continental) scales. Thus, WP8 integrates five tasks representing the four Research Challenges (RCs) at individual sites or platforms to support site-based, interdisciplinary, whole system research and a synthesis task.

Task 8.1 (Biodiversity loss) focused on determining and prioritising the stressors promoting biodiversity change, and identifying indicators for characterising long-term biodiversity trends. Task 8.2 (Biogeochemical controls of ecosystem functions) aimed to understand the impact of climate change and extreme weather events on C and N cycles. Task 8.3 (Climate-water-food nexus) evaluated the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and ecosystem resilience; and task 8.4 (Socio-ecological systems) aimed to advance understanding of stakeholder-defined local and regional environmental challenges. Further details can be found in the respective deliverables (D8.1-8.4).

Finally, the main goal of task 8.5 (synthesis task) was to evaluate the application of WAILS using data from eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms in Tasks 8.1-8.4. We analysed how long-term biodiversity, climate, hydrology, biogeochemistry and social-ecology data of selected eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms can contribute to the holistic understanding of the ecosystem response to anthropogenic stressors and extreme weather events. We evaluated the main difficulties encountered during the data compilation and analysis processes, and proposed steps forward for the correct application of the Whole System Approach. Moreover, we evaluated to which extent the eLTER Standard Observations (SOs) including related variables are already applied in the eLTER RI. Based on this evaluation, we provide a synthesis report on the current status of the eLTER RI with regard to the eLTER SOs and provide recommendations on how to further improve eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms to better align with the WAILS approach.

2 Summary of previous tasks

In this section, we summarise the analysis conducted and the results obtained from tasks 8.1-8.4, using a set of variables from different components (see **Table 1**). The main trends observed in D8.1-8.4 and complementary studies are summarised in **Table 2**.

2.1. Task 8.1. High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change

Summary:

- Long-term data from five case studies were used to analyse effects of anthropogenic stressors on biodiversity
- The datasets covered different taxonomic groups (birds, plants and freshwater macroinvertebrates)
- Overall, results showed significant responses of taxonomic and functional composition and metrics to environmental change

For this task we performed five case studies (see **Table 1**). The first three were presented in the Deliverable D8.1, while the two others were published in scientific articles (Baker et al. 2021, Nguyen et al. 2023). The main objective of these case studies was to determine and prioritise the anthropogenic stressors affecting short-term variability and long-term changes in biodiversity at the site and catchment scale. For this purpose we used five different datasets from five different eLTER Sites, covering different taxonomic groups (i.e. birds, plants and macroinvertebrates).

Deliverable D8.1 evaluates the stressors promoting biodiversity change, and identifies indicators for characterising long-term biodiversity trends at the site and catchment scale. In the Baixo-Sabor eLTER site (Portugal), we used cliff-nesting birds as ecological indicators of ecosystem resilience to anthropogenic changes and the construction of human infrastructures (i.e. river damming). Our results indicate a negative impact of damming on the population of Egyptian vultures. In the Doñana eLTER site (Spain), we used waterbirds as indicators of wetlands resilience to land use changes, flooding regime and vegetation dynamics. Overall, results showed declines in the abundance of waterbirds in 'dry hydrological years'. Similarly, in the Moor House eLTER site (United Kingdom), we used plant communities as indicators of peatland resilience to environmental changes. However, the lack of spatial variability in abiotic data in this case study impaired our ability to understand changes in plant community trends.

We also used as example a recently published paper from Baker et al. (2021). The main goal of this study was to determine and prioritise stressors affecting long-term changes in biodiversity. More specifically, this case study focused on evaluating the effects of climate warming, air pollution (i.e. acidification) and bark beetle infestations on the freshwater macroinvertebrate community. The study was carried out at the Taferlruck measuring station in the eLTER Site Bavarian Forest National Park (Germany). The authors used comprehensive long-term (1983–2014) datasets comprising high-resolution macroinvertebrate and physico-chemical data from a near-natural stream. Results showed that macroinvertebrate communities have undergone substantial changes over the past three decades, revealing an increase in overall community abundance (+173%) and richness (+51.6%), as well as taxonomic restructuring driven by a significant increase of dipterans abundance and richness. Before the year 2000, results indicated that decreases in sulphate deposition and the subsequent recovery from historical acidification were potential factors contributing to the increases in abundance and richness. These factors were considered more influential than increases in water temperature (1.5 °C overall increase from 1982 to 2014). However, after 2000, changes in nutrient cycling, caused by bark beetle infestations and rising temperatures, were associated with taxonomic restructuring. This restructuring resulted in disproportional increases of dipterans at the expense of sensitive taxa such as Plecoptera and Trichoptera. This study highlights the challenges when investigating the effects of climate change within a multi-stressor context, as the recovery from previous disturbances may obscure the impacts of ongoing disturbances like climate change. Overall, we observed strong community restructuring, demonstrating that stenothermal headwater communities face additional stress due to emerging competition with tolerant taxa. Thus, conservation efforts should consider the temporal variability of communities and their recovery from disturbances in order to adequately identify vulnerable and sensitive species.

Finally, we include an example of a recent study from Nguyen et al. (2023). Here, we used 10 years of annual monitoring data from 14 sampling sites in the eLTER Site Rhine-Main-Observatory (Germany) to evaluate spatiotemporal responses of freshwater macroinvertebrate communities to changes in ecological quality. In general, both taxonomic and trait metrics consistently reflected the magnitude of the improvements in land-use (i.e., reductions in the proportion of agricultural areas and increases in substrate diversity metrics) and water quality. However, community composition did not reflect this effect suggesting a weaker link between anthropogenic impact severity and changes in the macroinvertebrate community. This case study highlights the importance of accounting for the variability in community responses to changes in environmental quality, and identifying optimal monitoring strategies to track such responses.

2.2. Task 8.2. Biogeochemical response of ecosystems to drying and rewetting

Summary:

- Generalised additive models were run to analyse changes of greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes, soil moisture and soil temperature variables over the measured period (3 to 9 years) in two eLTER Sites (Hyytiälä SMEAR II, Finland; and Rosalia Lehrforst, Austria)
- Drought effects were more GHG-specific, but post-drought methane (CH₄) uptake was consistently affected by soil moisture dynamics
- There were clear and significant temporal changes in soil CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes over the measured timeframes
- We highlighted the importance of long-term measurements to detect and understand changes to biogeochemical (BGC) processes

The main goal of this task was to increase process understanding of the impact of climate change and extreme weather events (i.e. drought) on carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) cycling and feedback in different ecosystems. More specifically, we aimed to (a) identify critical environmental thresholds and tipping points in C and N turnover and fluxes and (b) improve our understanding of the impact of extreme weather events and climate change on ecosystem processes.

For this purpose, we collected biogeochemical legacy data from different eLTER Sites, homogenised, cleaned, gap-filled, and analysed. However, this process was not straight-forward and we faced multiple difficulties (e.g. missing metadata, large variety of data structures). As a result, the scientific product produced from this task studied the effects of soil drought on soil greenhouse gas fluxes (GHG, i.e. CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) over time at two different sites: a boreal, coniferous forest, Hyytiälä SMEAR II (Finland); and a temperate, broadleaf forest, Rosalia Lehrforst (Austria). We used soil temperature and moisture to identify soil drought events. After this, we used generalised additive models (GAM) to analyse the effects of drought events on GHG fluxes. Due to the data structure, it was not possible to clearly distinguish between changes caused by drought or indirect climate change effects (e.g. via on-going decreased precipitation or increased soil temperature). We suggest monitoring not only precipitation, but also soil water status, as drought is more complex than merely lack of precipitation. We found significant temporal changes in soil GHG fluxes over the measured timeframes at both eLTER sites. Results showed CO₂ and N₂O emissions to be more affected by drought and long-term trends at Hyytiälä with increased CO₂ emission and decreased N₂O emissions both following drought and over the entire measurement period. CH₄ uptake increased at both sites both during non-drought periods and as an overall multi year trend and was predominantly affected by soil moisture dynamics. Multiyear trends also suggest an increase in soil temperature in the boreal forest and a decrease in soil moisture in the temperate forest. These findings underline forests as an important sink for CH₄, possibly with an increasing rate in a future climate.

During this task other data products were generated, such as a dataset on water chemistry or a dataset on soil moisture and temperature (see **Table 1**). Although they were not yet analysed, they will be used in collaboration with other tasks (e.g. T9.3).

2.3. Task 8.3. Water use efficiency (WUE) of ecosystems and resilience to drought

Summary:

- Flux tower Eddy Covariance long term data were used to assess the impact of droughts on WUE using the Drought Response Index and the Resilience Index. These drought indices were determined for 25 drought events occurring in 10 forested stations.
- The results of this analysis showed that the GPP response is decreasing as the drought duration and intensity are increasing. This can be observed both at the European level as well as at the regional levels. However, it should be noted that at low drought index events we have a high variability of the GPP response.
- Flux tower data analysis indicated a significant resilience to drought events of forested sites
- The 1D-ICZ and the CLM5.0 models are capable of simulating successfully the primary production of the forested ecosystems and their water use efficiency
- Both the SWAT and the INCA-N watershed scale models were also able to simulate plant growth in agricultural and forested ecosystems respectively and assess the impact of drought on the water use efficiency of the vegetation
- All of the data needed to setup and calibrate the SWAT and INCA-N models could be obtained from publicly accessible open data sources from LTER sites

The main goal of this task was to improve our understanding on the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience, and to evaluate relationships between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience. For that purpose, we used three complementary methodologies (see also **Table 1**):

Time series analysis of flux tower data: We used flux tower long-term data to evaluate the impact of droughts on WUE. For this purpose, we selected 10 well-instrumented sites with good availability of long-term data, covering the whole Europe. The Drought and Resilience Indices results indicated a significant resilience to moderate and extreme drought events in European forested sites. Moreover, we found that the gross primary production (GPP) response decreases as the drought intensity and duration increases.

Data for WUE modelling with 1D-ICZ and CLM5.0 models: The objective of this analysis was to study the plant-soil-water system (i.e. the interactions between soil, water and plants) and assess the relationship between WUE and soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience in three eLTER sites. We used two models, the 1D-ICZ and the CLM5.0 models. For this analysis, we also used information regarding the vegetation, soil stocks of C, N, P, K, lysimeter chemistry, atmospheric chemistry and fertilisation loadings (see further detail on the modelling approach in deliverable D8.3). Results revealed that both models were able to successfully simulate the primary production of the forested ecosystems and their WUE.

Data for WUE modelling with watershed scale models: The final evaluation of this work dealt with the assessment of the watershed scale models to evaluate the impact of drought on WUE and GPP. Two different watershed models were used, the SWAT and the INCA-N models. SWAT was used to model the Koiliaris CZO (critical zone observatory) in Greece while INCA-N was used to model Svartberget catchment in Sweden covering in this way two extremes of Europe. The results were consistent with the flux tower analysis, indicating that biogeochemical models can be also used to study changes in ecosystem services as part of WAILES.

2.4. Task 8.4. Social-ecological analyses of stakeholder-defined local and regional environmental challenges

Summary:

- We conducted an in-depth land-use systems and stakeholder analysis using semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions in two eLTSER Platforms, characterising relevant actors, adaptation options and decision-making factors.
- We implemented a survey-based social network analysis in three eLTSER Platforms, analysing and assessing land-use and climate change related communication between relevant stakeholder groups.
- Results show how differently land use systems are organised in terms of land use structures, land use policies and regulations, and institutions relevant to land use decision-making in the regions. Consequently, interventions in land use systems must be considered highly regionally specific. These insights will help to expand and transfer land-use decision-making models to other study regions, as well as the development of eLTER Standard observations, social-ecological data products and eLTSER Platform design.

The main goal of this task was to gain a deeper understanding of stakeholder-defined local and regional environmental challenges. More specifically, the aim of Task 8.4. was to implement a social-ecological case study to analyse land-use and adaptation decision-making, to test the capability of the RI and designated eLTSER Platforms to provide required data for the transfer of an agent-based model, and to derive insights thereof for RI development. Due to the fact that the integration of social-ecological research questions and data from the social-ecological sphere into eLTER is still a relatively novel process without much precedent, we first opted for a top-down approach to inform the development of social-ecological Standard Observations, other data products and eLTSER Platform design characteristics through a series of guided discussions with leading experts from the Institute of Social Ecology at BOKU University Vienna. Complementing this, we opted to apply two complementary methodologies in eLTSER Platforms: (1) an in-depth land-use systems and stakeholder analysis using semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions (Eisenwurzen, Doñana), (2) a survey-based social network analysis (Eisenwurzen, Trnava, Montado) to produce new primary data for model development and to further inform eLTER Standard Observations and eLTSER Platform design.

The objective of the systems and actors analysis was to generate a profound understanding of the land-use systems, providing the qualitative basis for the land use decision-making model SECLAND (spatially-explicit agent-based model) expansion and transfer. This was achieved by qualitatively assessing the main challenges and conflicts related to land-use and climate change, as well as by identifying and characterising the most important land-use stakeholders, their adaptation options and decision-making factors. We therefore conducted 13 and 12 semi-structured interviews in the eLTSER Platforms Doñana and Eisenwurzen resp., and three focus group discussions in Doñana with local experts representing central land-use stakeholder groups. Environmental challenges in Doñana are mainly driven by land-use legacies and governance neglect over many decades. Additionally, the conflict is strongly exacerbated by climate change impacts and political rivalries in the past 10-12 years. Concurrent problems are deeply ingrained in the positioning of individual stakeholders. Farmers mainly perceive adaptation options in terms of additional infrastructure and technology, with economic considerations and climatic pressures, as well as tradition, being the most prominent decision-making factors. Other stakeholders such as the protected areas, NGOs, extension services and the scientific community challenge this view and demand reductions in production capacities and intensities. We identified three agricultural sectors (rice, olives and berries) to be implemented in the Doñana version of the model, which are strongly impacted by climate change and the prevailing land- and water-use conflict. Future work will also identify options, in collaboration with Task 9.4., to represent governance actors and other (non-agricultural) conflict parties in the model. Results

indicate that major differences between the land-use systems and their actors in Eisenwurzen and Doñana require changes to the agent-based model to make it more flexible and generally enable transferability to new regions.

The objective of the social network analysis was to gain a deeper understanding of the communication involved in land-use and adaptation decision-making. This analysis is relevant for the implementation of more pronounced agent interactions and social learning in the agent-based model. We conducted a survey in the eLTSER Platforms Eisenwurzen, Montado and Trnava, targeting local land-users and other land-use stakeholders. The survey included socio-demographic, farm-structural, climate change adaptation as well as network and communication variables. Results show that the most important communication partners in terms of frequency and influence are fellow land-users as well as public consultants such as the chambers of agriculture. The importance of other stakeholder groups differs significantly between the regions. While Eisenwurzen exhibits more frequent and influential communication with authorities, political representatives and protected areas, the scientific community was prominently rated only in Montado and Trnava. In Trnava, economic and market actors were among the most frequent/influential contacts. Montado's land-use network highlights the prominent role of Portuguese land-user associations and private consultants, with a subordinate role for economic and environmental actors.

2.5. Summary tables

Table 1. Datasets produced and case studies from tasks 8.1-8.4. In light grey, those datasets that have not been analysed yet due to lack of information or because they will be used in other tasks.

Task	Dataset	Sites	Years	Variables	No. of spheres	Objective	Analysis
8.1	Cliff-nesting birds	1 site (Baixo Sabor, Portugal)	12 (2010-2021)	Breeding occurrence and productivity of cliff-nesting birds	2 (Biosphere, Social-ecological sphere)	Evaluate changes in reproductive trends of priority conservation cliff-nesting bird species in relation to the Baixo Sabor hydropower dam installation and operation	Trend analysis (GLMM, BACI design)
8.1	Waterbirds	1 site (Doñana, Spain)	37 (1984-2020)	Taxonomic and functional metrics Land use, NDVI and hydrological variables	3 (Biosphere, Hydrosphere, Social-ecological sphere)	Understand how changes in land use, primary productivity and freshwater inundation affect the diversity and abundance of waterbird communities	Predictive modelling (GLMs)
8.1	Vegetation	1 site (Moor House, United Kingdom)	20 1996-2015	Plant community metrics Soil and climatic variables	3 (Biosphere, Atmosphere, Geosphere)	Identify stressors of biodiversity change by addressing biodiversity responses to environmental variation based on accompanying abiotic data	Trend analysis (multiple comparison, DCA, PCA)
8.1	Freshwater macroinvertebrates 1	1 site (Taferlruck measuring station, Germany)	32 (1983–2014)	32 community metrics (e.g. compositional and abundance metrics; richness and diversity metrics; tolerance and sensitivity metrics; proportion of functional groups) 15 water physico-chemical variables (e.g. DO, pH, water	4 (Biosphere, Hydrosphere, Social-ecological sphere, Atmosphere)	To evaluate the effects of climate warming, air pollution and bark beetle infestations on freshwater macroinvertebrates	Mann-Kendall trend analysis

Task	Dataset	Sites	Years	Variables	No. of spheres	Objective	Analysis
				temperature, nutrients and ions) and land-use variables			
8.1	Freshwater macroinvertebrates 2	14 sites in the Rhine-Main-Observatory (Germany)	10 (2010-2019)	13 taxonomic and 13 functional metrics (e.g. abundance, richness, diversity, etc) 8 environmental variables (precipitation, temperature, land-use, substrate index, runoff, total N, total P, salinity)	4 (Biosphere, Hydrosphere, Social-ecological sphere, Atmosphere)	Investigate spatiotemporal responses of stream macroinvertebrate communities along anthropogenic disturbance gradients	Trend analysis
8.2	Greenhouse gas fluxes	2 sites (Hyytiälä SMEAR II, Finland; and Rosalia Lehrforst, Austria)	Mean: 6.0 Range: 3-9	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , and N ₂ O fluxes Soil moisture and soil temperature	3 (Atmosphere, Hydrosphere Geosphere)	To understand historical drought and rewetting effects on biogeochemical processes	GAM
8.2	Water chemistry	1 site (Brasschaat, Belgium) <i>Zöbelboden site to be explored</i>	-	Dissolved organic carbon (DOC), ammonium (NH ₄ ⁺ -N), nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻ -N) as well as soil moisture and soil temperature		-	-
8.2	Soil moisture and temperature	79 sites (15 countries)	-	Soil moisture and soil temperature		-	-
8.3	Time series of flux tower data	10 sites (Brasschaat, Belgium; Rollesbroich, Germany; Selhausen, Germany; Wüstebach, Germany; Hyytiälä, Finland; Yatir, Israel; Renon, Italy; Collelongo-Selva Piana, Italy; Svartberget, Sweden; Zöbelboden, Austria)	Mean: 16.1 Range: 7-25	Gross Primary Production (GPP), Net Ecosystem Exchange (NEE), Latent heat flux, Air temperature, Ecosystem respiration and Soil water content. Water-use efficiency (WUE), Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI), Soil Moisture Deficit Index	4 (Biosphere, Hydrosphere, Atmosphere, Geosphere)	To evaluate the response of forested ecosystems across the continent to drought events as well as the resilience of the ecosystems to drought (meaning that they are capable of achieving substantial growth after the drought event).	Time series analysis

Task	Dataset	Sites	Years	Variables	No. of spheres	Objective	Analysis
				(SMDI), Drought Response Index and Resilience Index were calculated			
8.3	WUE modelling with 1D-ICZ and CLM5.0 models	3 sites (Zöbelboden, Austria; Hyytiälä, Finland; Svartberget, Sweden)	Mean: 24.3 Range: 23-25	Precipitation chemistry, Soil water chemistry, Throughfall chemistry, Runoff water chemistry, Groundwater chemistry, Litterfall chemistry, Soil structure, Vegetation, Tree growth, Biomass, as well as data from Meteorological station and Eddy covariance flux tower	4 (Biosphere, Hydrosphere, Atmosphere, Geosphere)	To study the plant-soil-water system and assess the relationship between WUE and soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience.	1D-ICZ and CLM5.0 models
8.3	WUE modelling with watershed scale models	2 sites(Koiliaris CZO, Greece and Svartberget Catchment, Sweden)	Mean: 32.0 Range: 23-41	Hydrologic data and river and groundwater chemistry data	3 (Hydrosphere, Atmosphere, Geosphere)	To study the ecosystem response to drought events at the watershed level	SWAT (applied in Koiliaris CZO) and INCA models (Svartberget Catchment)
8.4	Systems and stakeholder analysis	2 platforms (Eisenwurzen, Austria; Doñana, Spain)	-	Qualitative data on central land-use and climate change related challenges, stakeholders, adaptation measures and decision-making	1 (Social-ecological sphere)	To study the local land-use conflict, climate change impacts and adaptation decision-making as basis for SECLAND model transfer.	Semi-structured interviews, focus groups, content analysis
8.4	Social network analysis	3 platforms (Eisenwurzen, Austria; Montado, Portugal; Trnava, Slovakia)	-	Land-use communication and network data (contact, relation, frequency, influence, topics)	1 (Social-ecological sphere)	To improve understanding of land-use communication networks and identify relevant "opinion-forming" actors and points of intervention to influence land use decision-making.	(Online) Survey, Social network analysis

Table 2. Summary matrix illustrating the main relationships identified in the different case studies across the five spheres. Arrows up (↑) indicate positive relationships between the explanatory and response variables, while arrows down (↓) indicate negative relationships between the explanatory and response variables.

Response variable		Explanatory variable				
		Atmosphere	Social and economic sphere	Biosphere	Hydrosphere	Geosphere
Social and economic sphere	Climate change impacts and adaptation options (D8.4)	-	Stakeholder group type Farm type	-	-	-
	Communication and network variables (D8.4)	-	Stakeholder group type Farm type	-	-	-
	Cliff nesting birds productivity (D8.1)	-	Dam construction and operation ↓	-	-	-
	Diversity of waterbirds (D8.1)	-	-	-	Dry hydrological year ↓	-
Biosphere	Abundance of waterbirds (D8.1)	-	-	-	Dry hydrological year ↓	-
	Abundance of freshwater invertebrates (Baker et al. 2021)	Sulphate deposition ↓	-	-	Total organic carbon ↑	-
	Richness of freshwater invertebrates (Baker et al. 2021)	Sulphate deposition ↓	-	-	-	-
	Abundance of freshwater invertebrates (Nguyen et al. 2023)	Precipitation ↓	-	-	-	-
	Richness of freshwater invertebrates (Nguyen et al. 2023)	Temperature ↓ Precipitation ↑	Land use index ↓	-	Substrate index ↑	-
	Gross primary production (D8.3)	Temperature ↑ Precipitation ↓	-	-	Dry hydrological year ↓	Geochemical leaching ↓
Hydrosphere	Plant evapotranspiration (D8.3)	Temperature ↑	-	-	Dry hydrologic year ↑	-
	Drought Response Index (D8.3)	Temperature ↑ Precipitation ↓	-	-	Dry hydrological year ↓	Geochemical leaching ↓
	Resilience Index (D8.3)	Temperature ↑ Precipitation ↓	-	-	Dry hydrological year ↓	Geochemical leaching ↓

Geosphere	Soil CO ₂ emissions (D8.2, Gillespie et al. 2024)	-	-	-	Drought (in boreal environment) ↑	-
	Soil N ₂ O emissions (D8.2., Gillespie et al. 2024)	-	-	-	Drought ↓	-
	Soil CH ₄ uptake (D8.2., Gillespie et al. 2024)	-	-	-	-	Soil temperature ↑ Soil moisture ↓

Table 2 summarises the main relationships identified in the different case studies across the five spheres. It shows the strong role of atmosphere (e.g. temperature and precipitation) and hydrosphere (e.g. dry hydrological year and drought) as explanatory variables in the case studies conducted. However, our results suggest that the social-economic sphere should also probably play a more important role as an explanatory variable, if/where this is taken into account. In addition, results showed highly variable responses depending on the ecosystem that is analysed (e.g. the effect of drought on CO₂ soil emissions was higher in boreal ecosystems).

3 Further development of the eLTER RI to improve research on global change

One of the main objectives of these case studies was to evaluate and demonstrate the added value of long-term harmonised data from different spheres for analysing the impact of global change. Here, we summarise the lessons learned after working with eLTER data, the difficulties encountered, the importance of standard observations and legacy data. In this chapter we also provide suggestions on how to improve data sampling procedures and data flows.

3.1. Current fitness of the eLTER RI and difficulties encountered

The case studies conducted in WP 8 demonstrate that we have already developed the tools, methods and models to analyse the data generated in eLTER Sites and to evaluate the effects of anthropogenic stressors, including climate change and extreme events on European ecosystems. However, experts within the different tasks highlighted several obstructions that were encountered during the process of compiling and analysing the data (Table 3). First of all, we had difficulties during the initial site selection process, as the main objective was to conduct these case studies using eLTER Sites and eLTER Platforms aiming to measure all relevant WAILS components (geosphere, biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere, social-ecological sphere) simultaneously. With the time and funding available, we were not able to gather data from a site covering all WAILS components, and therefore, it was not possible to apply a direct approach in order to test the eLTER Whole System Approach with the current data. In addition, the absence or insufficient quality of detailed data inventories and associated metadata made it challenging to identify and select sites with desired data requirements, placing heavy dependence on data collectors for filling information gaps. To overcome these issues, we focused on sites with consistent data on at least two out of the five spheres of the WAILS approach.

During the data collection process, we detected additional difficulties. For instance, many eLTER Sites had slow responses to data calls, and some of them never responded due to difficulties in finding or retrieving the data and the scarce digitalization in some cases. This often required contacting the person who was knowledgeable of the data and the time to reshape the data into the appropriate format. We also found that even data subjected to quality controls had odd values (e.g. flat-lined data, outliers, impossible values), and required contacting the data collector for verification. Occasionally, we were not able to obtain all the necessary data to conduct a specific case study on one site from a single data provider and we had to contact several data providers (see e.g. deliverable 8.3). While all of these issues have made our work more difficult, we recognise that site managers are constrained by limited time and funding.

To conclude, the use of different measurement methods and sampling protocols over time at certain sites is disrupting the continuity of the time series. This is a relevant issue, especially when legacy data are combined with new acquired data, and when new measurement protocols differ from those used in the past, requiring complex harmonisation efforts or the application of appropriate statistical approaches and models.

Note that these issues have been expected and were driving forces for the implementation of the eLTER RI. eLTER addresses data issues through the harmonisation of measurement protocols (many of them existing in other monitoring programs) and tools that allow for the merge of historical and newly gathered data.

3.2. Relevance of Standard Observations

The compilation of standardised data covering large temporal and spatial extents is fundamental to address research challenges of global relevance and is one of the most critical points in the process of developing the eLTER RI and its associated services (Skidmore et al. 2015, Kissling et al. 2018, Haase et al. 2018). Despite some essential variables to understand climate, biodiversity, and other environmental changes, as well as a global biodiversity observing system (GBIOS) to coordinate monitoring worldwide have already been proposed (e.g. Essential Biodiversity Variables, Essential Climate Variables, Essential Ocean Variables) (Pereira et al. 2013, Navarro et al. 2017, Gonzalez et al. 2023), there is still no harmonised observation system established for obtaining this standardised data (Pereira et al. 2013). Regarding climate change, the most high profile annual global monitoring assessment report covers mainly the physical spheres (e.g. bio-geochemical processes, water use efficiency) and delivers annually for all states (Intergovernmental Panel of Climate Change, i.e. IPCC Assessment Report, 2023). There are also various ongoing efforts to establish essential variables for evaluating Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to provide a framework for coordinated action across policy domains (Reyers et al. 2017, Lehmann et al. 2020, 2022, Masó et al. 2020, Plag and Jules-Plag 2020), however the lack of a harmonised system persists also for socio-ecological research.

Thus, one of the main objectives of eLTER is to define and establish a minimum set of key Standard Observations (SOs) and their associated protocols that can characterise adequately the state and future trends of the Earth systems (see Deliverable D3.1) (Haase et al. 2018, Mollenhauer et al. 2018). This will ultimately help to apply the eLTER's Whole System Approach and to overcome some of the difficulties that we have currently encountered in our case studies. Based on our experience, we have seen that almost no site has, to this day, the capacity/resources to conduct SOs in all the spheres considered by WAALS. We therefore believe that it is necessary to provide sites with the infrastructure and know-how to carry out observations in all spheres.

Based on our experience with the Case Studies, we found that data collection in most eLTER Sites was not consistent over time and, therefore, we were not able to obtain long time series. However, there are some exceptions related to sites being part of long-term monitoring networks such as International Cooperative Programmes (ICPs) and the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS). In addition, since social-ecological sphere SOs (i.e. SOSOCs) have not been defined before and it was not yet compulsory for eLTER Platforms to collect specific social-ecological data, we did not receive standardised and harmonised data from the social-ecological sphere across designated eLTER Platforms. In the future eLTER RI, SOSOCs connected to the themes of governance, land use, and ecosystem services, will be collected on the basis of specific surveys, interview panels, document analysis or expert judgement (see Deliverable D3.1 and D3.2).

Our results revealed the importance of ensuring the spatial-temporal overlap between a broad range of abiotic, biotic and social-ecological variables for the comprehensive implementation of the WAALS. Tight co-location of stressor and response variables including appropriate measurement frequencies is of course ideal, but may often be impractical/unaffordable. In some cases it may be however possible to draw inferences from intensive measurements made at one point, if coupled with less intensive but more spatially extensive measurements across a wider site.

In conclusion, the case studies conducted in WP8 were limited to very few sites, insufficiently reflecting the social-ecological heterogeneity across Europe (see also WP9 results for further details). During pre-labelling of Sites and Platforms across Europe in the year 2023 and 2024 promising numbers resulted, hence, the eLTER RI is on a good track to overcome these issues. We strongly believe that having access to the full set of harmonised SOs across eLTER Sites and eLTER Platforms will significantly improve model performance, and enable a wide variety of ecological and social-

ecological research covering the main themes of resource use, land use, management of ecosystems, consumption, social-ecological transformations and integrated social-ecological modelling.

3.3. Relevance of legacy data

“Legacy data” refers to existing data that were collected in eLTER sites in the past for purposes other than the current research or monitoring objectives (see Deliverable 4.1). These data may have been collected using different methods, instruments, or quality standards, and may cover different time periods. The term “legacy data”, in most cases, implies that these data are already available and may be useful for current or future studies, although they often require additional processing or integration to be effectively utilised in a specific research context.

Legacy data are extremely valuable as they contain information spanning several decades. Based on our experience with these case studies, integrating legacy data appropriately is, to this day, crucial for assessing long-term changes in European ecosystems. Otherwise, the availability of data is greatly diminished, and our potential to evaluate long-term trends is reduced. In fact, our case studies rely almost entirely on legacy data since eLTER Standard Observations are currently only being developed.

In order to better implement legacy data into the WAILS approach, improving communication with the respective site managers and, ideally, with the persons involved in gathering the data is fundamental. In the specific case of legacy data from the social-ecological sphere, there may exist the opportunity for eLTER Platforms to create a genuine data product called “Environmental history profile” (working title), covering land- and resource-use legacies on a regional scale, including legacy and third-party data, such as archival, cadastral, remotely sensed, quantitative and qualitative data sources relevant for WAILS research approaches targeting historical timeframes. Local institutions holding such data can be academic or private research institutes, museums, private or public archives, or certain civil society groups and organisations.

However, we need to be aware of the limitations of legacy data, which would need to be collected on a case-to-case basis, and which may deviate from recent/current datasets in terms of methods and temporal/spatial resolution. For instance, in the case of SOSOCs (which will only be collected by eLTER Platforms), legacy data will probably not be available in sufficient consistency, detail or thematic coverage. In order to better align legacy data with SOs, we believe that a “transition period”, where both SOs and former variables are compiled jointly for several years, would be extremely valuable. This will eventually allow a direct comparison of legacy data with the new SOs and not to lose the work done so far, as much of the legacy data may be complementary and still of great relevance (further details in Deliverable D10.4).

Additionally, to effectively integrate legacy data with new SOs, it is crucial to enhance both the quality and quantity of current metadata. At present, the available metadata is often insufficient or inconsistent, which significantly impedes the effective utilisation and integration of these valuable historical data sets with modern observations. Improving metadata standards will enable a more seamless and accurate merging of past and present data, thereby enriching the overall understanding and analysis of ecosystem dynamics.

3.4. Relevance for Site and Platform design

Many eLTER Sites have been set up and maintained for different purposes, e.g. in the frame of research projects, and are therefore often lacking a standardised design and equipped with a diverse array of long-term monitoring components. On the other hand, many eLTER Sites belong to long-term monitoring systems (e.g. ICP Forests, ICP Integrated Monitoring) or Research Infrastructures (e.g. ICOS), where measurement designs are highly standardised. Nonetheless, overall, eLTER Sites are

currently very heterogeneous. To overcome this issue, eLTER has developed not only the SOs mentioned above, but also standardised Site and Platform categories stratified by monitoring intensity and considering the main habitat type selected by the respective site manager. Accordingly, eLTER Sites will be categorised as Category 1 sites (i.e. sites covering all eLTER Standard Observations of all spheres with the basic method but specialised on at least 2 spheres, where the prime method is accomplished) and Category 2 sites (i.e. sites covering all ecosystem components and their related Standard Observations measured with the basic method). The combination of both categories will help to increase the density of sites in the eLTER RI, thereby expanding the temporal and spatial representativeness. However, even though the designs have been developed, at the site level, alignment with their different purposes (monitoring, ICOS etc.) will be challenging.

Similarly, Category 1 eLTSER Platforms will collect all SOSOCs with the prime method, while Category 2 will collect SOSOCs with the basic method. The eLTSER Platform classification requires at least one eLTER Site to be located within the platform boundaries. However, in order to implement the Whole System Approach at the platform scale, it is important to have comprehensive monitoring stations covering the main ecosystems within the area. This will include the ability to adequately model all ecosystems and the whole platform. Once we have modelled the bio-geophysical domain of the platform, we can link it to the social-ecological domain with stakeholder involvement, explore alternatives and identify sustainable management of landscapes. Thus, if an eLTSER Platform had a number of well-equipped sites within its boundaries, this would probably enable much more fine-grained WAIS research. However, integrating smaller site-level scales with larger platform-level scales needs to be done on a case-by-case basis depending on the methodologies applied in a given WAIS research approach.

3.5. Services

In addition to the establishment of standard protocols to measure different variables, our results highlight the importance of the development of standardised workflows for data management, processing and exchange. Ensuring data digitization, creating reliable inventories of variables and sites, developing automated workflows for updating datasets with newly acquired data, implementing quality controls, and including comprehensive metadata will make the data more open and FAIR to the research community (Kissling et al. 2015). Thus, based on the difficulties encountered in the case studies conducted in this work package, here we provide some recommendations on how to improve data acquisition procedures and data flows:

- Data submission: Metadata and data acquisition processes should be further standardised, expanded and enforced in order to enable more specific queries and to avoid heterogeneous datasets. We suggest that the eLTER RI should provide templates (see e.g. Peterseil and Geiger 2020) and tools as part of the cyberinfrastructure that enable site managers to check the completeness of information and compliance before submitting datasets and their associated metadata to central eLTER data services (see e.g. Offenthaler 2024).
- Data checking and curation: For example, an upload system for file-based data with integrated quality checks (structure, missing or incorrect information, formats of variables) would secure data quality and facilitate subsequent data storage, handling and usage. In addition, workflows and tools should be implemented in order to identify potential errors in the datasets (e.g. double data entries, typing errors in species or site names, incorrect coordinates, etc.) and to harmonise specific variables. Ideally, these procedures should be implemented in the central eLTER data services.
- Data discovery and use: User interfaces should be implemented to facilitate access to the data by the scientific community.
- Data retrieval: Ideally, central eLTER data services would provide interfaces to obtain site-specific data from external data sources (i.e. third party data). This would enable easy access

to, for instance, climate data, land cover data and other remote sensing products, and trait data.

In addition, we want to highlight the necessity of sufficient, permanent and dedicated staff in eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms to enable not only PRIME method data collection, but also establishment of long-term collaboration with regional stakeholders, creation of additional data products and handling of social-ecological Transnational and Remote Access (TA/RA) requests.

Table 3. Summary of the main obstructions that were encountered in the case studies, proposed steps forward to overcome these issues, and measures already taken.

Obstructions	Steps forward	Measures taken
<i>Inconsistent data collection over time</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Define a set of key SOs and their associated protocols •Improve communication with site managers and with the persons involved in gathering the data to integrate legacy data •Establish a “transition period”, where both SOs and former variables are compiled jointly during some years 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Discussion and definition of key SOs (see D3.2) •Development of workflows for retrieval and harmonisation of legacy data (see D4.1) •Matching of SOs and former variables has already started
<i>No eLTER Site with data available for the five spheres</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ensure the spatial-temporal overlap between abiotic, biotic and social-ecological variables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •List of SOs covering all spheres finalised and mandatory for all eLTER RI sites (see D3.2)
<i>Absence of detailed inventories and metadata</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Improve current data and metadata standards •Enforce the implementation and curation of data following these standards •Data submission process should be further standardised •Improve data and metadata checking and curation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Development of specifications for data reporting and description of the structure (columns, fields) and content (description) of the data-reporting template (see e.g. Peterseil and Geiger 2020)
<i>Scarce data digitization and slow responses to data calls</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Implementation of user interfaces to facilitate access to the data by the scientific community •Develop interfaces to obtain site-specific data from external data sources (i.e. third party data) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Discussion on accelerating digitalisation of data has already been started (see e.g. D4.1)

3.6. Upscaling in social-ecological research

Social-ecological systems (SES) are usually studied at the local to regional scale in order to capture the nuanced interaction, feedbacks, and context-dependency of both (the social and the ecological) systems (Dirnböck et al. 2013, Mirtl et al. 2013). However, as SES are becoming more globally interconnected, the desire to study them at larger spatial scales is increasing (Dressler et al. 2022). As such, one of the primary justifications for the creation of a *network* of eLTSER Platforms, similarly to

eLTER Sites, is the dual desire to 1) develop theories about social-ecological system function that hold true across systems, and 2) understand how changes at broad scales (e.g., global climate change or implementation of new EU biodiversity policies) affect smaller scale SES similarly or differently and vice versa.

eLTER socio-ecological research has traditionally taken three forms: research within a single Platform (e.g., Berthet et al. 2022), comparative studies between a small number of Platforms (this provides initial support for the value of upscaling in social-ecological research) (e.g., Holzer et al. 2019), and theoretical research (e.g., Ohl et al. 2010). In this WP, we contributed to the upscaling in social-ecological research in two ways. First, as summarised in section 2.4 of this report, we developed and refined an agent-based model for generalizable application to LTSER platforms to study land use decision making processes (Gaube et al. 2024), and we conducted a social network analysis of three platforms to compare and identify similarities between them in communications and decision making processes among platform actors (Bertsch-Hörmann et al. 2024). Second, we contributed to a set of standard observations that will (ideally) enable cross-platform research on human interactions with biodiversity and the environment.

We are aware that, due to the inherent complexity of these systems, with factors becoming more or less important at different scales of analysis, and lack of large-scale spatial or temporal data sets (Dressler et al. 2022), upscaling SES research requires more than simply cross-platform comparisons. Therefore, the tasks completed in this WP should be viewed as the first modest, though necessary, steps towards establishing eLTER as an RI with seamless compatibility for multi-scalar research on SES. By refining our models for use in diverse SES contexts, and establishing our Standard Observation variables to be collected systematically across the European SES landscape, we offer robust methodologies and harmonised data sets for upscaling.

Complementary to our WP, WP9 focused on the optimisation of the eLTER Network design at the pan-European scale, with a particular interest in elucidating the interplay between continental scale policies and impact as mitigated through local and regional scale SES, and then upscaling again to explore broad policy impacts. Indeed, the eLTER WAILS approach and its commitment to collection of socio-ecological, abiotic and biodiversity standard observations at eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms, will provide the empirical foundation for such research on human impacts across Europe's diverse social ecological system.

Outputs at the site scale may be used to validate results at the continental scale and provide a more mechanistic understanding of the processes underlying global change, while projections at the continental scale may be used to integrate the effect of global stressors at the local level. In this context, our current research highlights the need for identification of multiple-scale stressors, i.e. local stressors (e.g. land use/cover) versus global stressors (e.g. climate change) to address the combined effect of anthropogenic and/or environmental drivers at the site and catchment level.

3.7. Benefits of eLTER

With the tasks carried out in this WP, we have seen that being part of the eLTER RI provides unique value and benefits that are unattainable without this network. It enables excellent research output and fosters collaboration on a continental scale, significantly enhancing our ability to address complex environmental challenges. When eLTER is involved, outcomes will significantly improve, serving a broader range of communities and providing better integration between the Grand Challenges, rather than addressing them separately. Additionally, the eLTER RI facilitates support for political decision-making by providing vital data and insights. This comprehensive approach is highly valued by national research funds and attracts significant funding opportunities, further promoting advancements in environmental research.

4 Concluding remarks

In this deliverable, we outline and discuss the difficulties encountered, the lessons learned after working with eLTER in-situ data, and the benefits of being part of the eLTER RI. Although we have already developed the methods and tools to analyse the data generated in eLTER Sites, we encountered several obstructions during the application of WAILS using data from eLTER Sites and eLTER Platforms. In fact, not all the original goals were achievable with the eLTER data that currently was made available. For instance, we did not find any site measuring relevant variables for all spheres simultaneously. This significant gap highlights the need for comprehensive data collection sites that can address the full spectrum of social and ecological variables (see also Ohnemus et al. 2023). The absence of such sites limits the effectiveness of current research and conservation efforts, as it hinders the ability to obtain a holistic understanding of ecological and socio-ecological dynamics. Thus, we believe that for the correct implementation of WAILS it is necessary to:

1. Define a set of mandatory key SOs.
2. Do not interrupt data collection, and ensure the information flow of datasets in order to guarantee general access to good quality data.
3. Increase the number of comprehensive stations in order to cover the main ecosystems within a Platform.
4. Ensure the spatial-temporal overlap between a broad range of abiotic, biotic and socio-economic variables for the comprehensive implementation of the WAILS.
5. Integrate legacy data appropriately. However, we need to be aware of the limitations of this type of data, which would need to be collected on a case-to-case basis, and which may deviate from recent/current datasets in terms of methods and temporal/spatial resolution.
6. Develop standardised workflows for data management, processing and sharing.
7. Improve data and metadata standards and enforce their proper implementation.

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